

Speculation on Lorentz Invariant Information Associated with Quantum $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$

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In information theory, $\ln(\text{probability}(i))$ equals information. The approach of maximization of Shannon's entropy $- \sum P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$ subject to a constraint $\sum e_i P(e_i)$ yields: $\ln(P(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ where e_i is a conserved piece of information associated with an interaction and $-1/T$, a Lagrange multiplier. In the case of tossing a die or coin, the constraint is $\sum P(i)$, so the Lagrange multiplier is not important, but $\sum P(e_i)$ is the conserved quantity and is associated with interactions i.e. trial runs.

In the case of a quantum free particle, one may ask: Where is the probability and where are the trial runs or interactions? A free particle, classically, has an energy and momentum as well as a time and x associated with $v=\text{constant}=x/t$. There do not seem to be any reactions so it is not clear what constraint exists, nor is it clear that there is any probability present as E, p and $v=x/t$ are deterministic.

In this note, we speculate on the relevant information and the presence of probability for a free particle. Such a particle does not seem to be probabilistic at first glance but, we argue that its intrinsic probability is not defined through interactions (like the classical statistical gas), but rather is inherent due to the various different ways it may have been formed. We argue that it creates other visible probabilities that are not based on maximization of entropy subject to a constraint.

Information in the Classical World

Classical statistical mechanics is often associated with the maximization of Shannon's entropy $- \sum P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$ subject to a constraint, say $\sum e_i P(e_i)$. This constraint is not arbitrary in the sense that it seems to be linked with a conserved quantity associated with interactions which create equilibrium. For a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, e_i is kinetic energy $pp/2m$ in the absence of $V(x)$. In other words, e_i is the conserved information which a particle carries into a reaction. The result of the above maximization of entropy subject to the constraint is:

$$\ln(P(e_i)) = -e_i/T \text{ where } -1/T \text{ is a Lagrange multiplier ((1))}$$

One could have started directly with ((1)) and bypassed maximization of entropy, i.e. $\ln(P)=$ conserved relevant information which is a result which exists in information theory. In the case of tossing a coin or die, there are no inter-coin or inter-die reactions and so $\sum P(i)$ is the conserved quantity which changes in a reaction and the constraint is $\sum P(e_i)\ln(P(e_i))$. Rather the trial runs represent the interactions.

In both the Maxwell-Boltzmann and coin/die examples, there is clear probability and a clear conserved quantity associated with either interactions or trial runs. A quantum free particle exists in Newtonian mechanics and does not seem to be associated with any probability. Furthermore, it is a free particle because it is not interacting and it is not clear if it is associated with any trial runs. How is it then that quantum mechanics associates a free particle with a two-dimensional type of probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$?

Special Relativity

Consider the classical case of a particle with rest mass m_0 (energy $m_0 c^2$) sitting at $x=0$. If there is a clock on the wall, one may argue that time passes and may be measured. There appear to be no interactions in this scenario and no probability. If the clock is removed, one might even go so far as to argue that there is no time if no interactions occur ever.

As a first step, we argue that it seems there is time. This follows from the Lorentz invariant:

$$-Et + px = \text{constant in frames moving with constant velocity } v \quad ((2))$$

In terms of information, $-Et + px$ is unusual in that one would normally consider E, p, x and t as separate pieces of information and not combine them in a way that yields a Lorentz invariant. Given that x and t have meaning for $v > 0$, we argue they should have meaning in the limit $v \rightarrow 0$. As a result, the Lorentz invariant for $v=0$ is:

$$-Et = -m_0 c^2 t \quad ((3))$$

Is there any physical scenario one may possibly attribute to ((3))? We suggest one may consider m_0 as consisting of dm 's and t as dt 's, In such a case:

$$M_0 t / (dt \, dm) = (\text{number of } dm \text{ pieces in } M) * (\text{number of } dt \text{ pieces in } t) \quad ((4))$$

Et is proportional to the number of ways one may assemble dm 's in a time t in order to create an m_0 at the time t . The larger t , the larger this number. This suggests that a particle with rest mass m_0 at time t is linked with a set of possible creation scenarios from $t=0$ to time t . These then are associated with probability. An immediate problem is that $m_0 t$ increases in time, whereas a particle with rest mass m_0 seems to sit unchanged. We consider this issue, but first we wish to compare different rest masses m_1 and m_2 at time t .

$M_1 t$ and $m_2 t$ should be proportional to the number of creation schemes associated with both. For $t_1 = \text{constant}/m_1$ and $t_2 = \text{constant}/m_2$, the number of creation schemes are the same for both rest masses, i.e. they represent the same probability. If one considers $-m_0 c^2 t$ as being a Lorentz invariant piece of information (equivalent to $-Et + px$ in other frames), then information theory could suggest that:

$$\ln(P(m_0)) = -m_0 c^2 t \quad ((5))$$

The problem is that this probability grows in time which contradicts the idea of a rest mass simply sitting in place. If one retains the idea of $m_0 t$ representing inherent information because it is linked to the number of ways to assemble m_0/dm pieces in a time t , one may try to reconcile this with a kind of invariance in time, but replacing $-m_0 c^2 t$ with $-i m_0 c^2 t$. This leads to a periodic (complex or two dimensional probability)

$$P(m_0 t) = \exp(-i m_0 c^2 t) \quad ((6))$$

At first one may object to such a quantity, given that $\exp(-ei/T)$ for an MB gas and $P(i) = 1/\text{number of outcomes}$ for a die or coin are real. The latter, however, are associated with interactions or trial runs, whereas a free particle has no such situation. Rather, an intrinsic probability is associated with the Lorentz invariant -mot associated with its construction scenarios in time t (broken into dts) from dm's. This suggests probability and a difference between m_0 and m_1 rest masses.

In the case of a frame moving with constant velocity v , one has $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. The minus sign ensures that the information:

$$-iEt+ipx \text{ remains constant for } t \rightarrow t+\text{constant}/E \text{ and } x \rightarrow x+\text{constant}/p \quad ((7))$$

X and t appear as independent, so the overall Lorentz invariant information $-Et+px$ may be viewed as the sum of two informations $-Et$ and px . In previous notes, we argued that formally one may maximize Shannon's entropy $-P(t)\ln(P(t))$ or $-P(x)\ln(P(x))$ subject to the constraint $-iEtP(t)$ or $ipxP(x)$ and treat E or p as Lagrange multipliers, but it seems that $-Et$ and px represent the information and one may use 1 as the Lagrange multiplier.

As a result, what appears to be a deterministic situation of a particle with rest mass m_0 sitting at $x=0$, may actually be linked to probability because there are Et (proportional) ways to create it such that m_0 exists at time t . An immediate question is: What are the implications of the unusual inherent probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$? Newtonian mechanics does not consider such an object so does it allow one to solve practical, experimentally verifiable, problems?

Inherent Probability and interactions

In Newtonian mechanics as well as in statistical mechanics there exist interactions. Even tossing a die or coin may be considered to be an interaction. $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, however, is associated with a particle with E, p which is not interacting. What happens if there is an interaction? We consider the case of $\exp(ipx)$. Analogous to the mot case, p may be broken into dp pieces and x into dx ones. Then px is proportional to the number of ways p may be assembled over a distance x . If p receives an impulse hit (say from a potential $V(x)$ or a sharp change from V_1 to V_2 (constant potentials).at x , then $p \rightarrow p_1$. The probability is now $\exp(ip_1x)$ where p_1x is proportional to the number of ways that p_1 may be assembled over a distance x , even though the p_1-p extra momentum was added at x . There seems to be an intrinsic probability associated with the number of ways that p_{total} may be created over x , because given a p , one does not know it is history of creation. Thus $\exp(ipx)$ plays a role in direct impulse hits.

One specific physical problem where such direct impulse hits occur is for a particle with rest mass m_0 and momentum p (nonrelativistically) traveling in a region with constant potential V_1 . At $x=0$, the potential suddenly changes to the constant value V_2 , but energy remains the same. Then there is a reflected probability $B\exp(-ipx)$ (where B is a weight) and a piece in region 2, $C\exp(ip_2x)$. Instead of maximization of Shannon's entropy, one uses continuity of these probabilities at x as well as their first derivative. This leads to two equations. Taking the complex conjugate of one and multiplying by the other, yields an expression $1-BB=CC$ or $1=BB+CC$ which is a conservation of probability equation. The inherent probability in $x \exp(ipx)$ disappears,

but gives rise to a different probability conservation scheme which does not follow from maximization of entropy. N-slit interactions are another example.

Duality xp in the Lorentz Invariant

Because the Lorentz invariant involves products of observables, i.e. $-Et$ and px , in the case of px , $\exp(ipx)$ may have two different interpretations. Consider an ensemble of constant p values. Then:

$$W(x)=\text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((8))$$

Here $\exp(ipx)$ represents the intrinsic x probability associated with a constant p .

Alternatively:

$$a(p)=\text{momentum wavefunction} = \text{Integral } dx \exp(-ipx) W(x) \quad ((9))$$

In this case, $\exp(-ipx)$ represents the probability of p for fixed x .

History in the Inherent Probability

We argued that mot is proportional to the number of ways m_0/dm small masses may be assembled during a time t , with each being added in a time dt . This led to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ as an inherent probability somehow linked with the probability of possible past histories of a particle with energy E at t and p at x . To see further how this complex probability is linked with a sense of history, one may note that a phase shift $\exp(ipx + iphase)$ changes the probability. Again, the phase shift may occur in many different ways, i.e. one piece at one x_1 etc. The particular information of a specific history is not present, but the overall phase is and leads to interference with another particle with only $\exp(ipx)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that although a particle with rest mass m_0 may seem to be unchanging and unassociated with time as no interactions occur, the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px = -m_0c^2t$, suggests m_0 is directly associated with time through mot . This quantity, however, does not seem to be linked with any kind of probability as no interaction or trial run occurs. We suggest there exists an intrinsic probability associated with the manner in which m_0 may have been created so that it is m_0 at time t . If one breaks m_0 into dm pieces and t into dt , then mot is proportional to the number of ways that one may create mot . If one has two rest masses m_0 and m_1 then, mot for $t=\text{constant}/m_0$ and m_1t_1 for $t_1=\text{constant}/m_1$ have the same inherent probability. If one considers this to be the relevant information, then from information theory: $\ln(P)=m_0c^2t$ or $P=\exp(m_0c^2t)$. This, however, leads to a growing probability. We suggest that to be consistent with the idea of m_0 not changing in time, one use $P=\exp(-im_0c^2t)$. This is a complex probability, but does not represent the result of an interaction or trial run. It is a different

kind of probability, an inherent one. Using a Lorentz transformation, one has: $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. "t" and x seem to be independent, so $\exp(ipx)$ represents an intrinsic probability in px. We argue that this form has physical consequences in that it describes interference/diffraction from n-slits and reflection/refraction from interfaces of different constant potential. Furthermore a phase shift $\exp(ipx+i \text{ phase shift})$ indicates a different set of history scenarios than $\exp(ipx)$ and these two interfere. This may be extended to a photon which also has the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$, even though it has not rest mass.